

THE IRONY OF AFRICAN RELIGIOSITY

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Abstract: It could be said that no man is born without a certain level of religious consciousness; but that of the African is exceedingly made manifest in his personality and world view. This explains why the African has been identified as highly religious. The central concern of this paper is that the more religious the African becomes/claims to be, the more evil and inhuman he appears to become. In other words, his religiosity appears to offer him nothing but a refuge to hide his evil and inhuman tendencies. It is upon this that this paper asks: what does it really mean to be religious? Is religiosity the same thing with morality? What is the relevance of religiosity without morality? What is the relationship between religiosity and morality? It is from this perspective that this paper defends the thesis that African religiosity has ironically enhanced his existential inauthenticity and inhumanity. At the end, this paper shall expose the African to certain existentialist principles that will facilitate his authenticity and prove how religiosity without morality is only but a mere human participation to fulfil social obligation. It shall expose the African to the real knowledge of morality and the guiding principles to an objective concept of morality. In doing this, the paper shall adopt an expository method to critically evaluate the African religiosity.

Introduction

The fact of the religiosity of the African is too obvious in what makes the African the person he is. But in its scholarly perspective, it was John

Samuel Mbiti, among others, who reiterated this when he asserts that the African is ‘notoriously’ religious, hence the implication that he does not know how to live irreligiously. The implication is

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that he perceives not just his own existence, but existence from a general sense of it, religiously. This feature of the African has a profound influence on the African that he even conceives nature religiously hence he seeks unification with nature/reality through religion. It is upon this consciousness that he attributes piety to natural phenomena as tools or objects of approach and symbols through which the divine is communicated with. The African world-view is also conceived in this realm of religious consciousness when the African universe is not perceived just socially horizontal, but also ontologically vertical. By this, the visible beings remain in constant and non-disjointed universe with the invisible beings. The African universe thus becomes conceived as socio-ontological hence the world of the visible interweaves and dovetails into the world of the invisible. Drawing from this, the African has been conceived by scholars not familiar with this conceptual scheme, as animistic, fetish, essentially naturalist/materialist, physicalist, idolatrous, diabolical, necromantic, etc. However, no matter the ontological-status of the African universe which supposedly presupposes the religious consciousness of the African being, the fundamental concern is to know whether the African has the real knowledge of religion.

Thus the paper asks: what is truly religion? What does it mean to be religious and what is the relationship between religiosity and morality. A proper address of these questions leads to the thesis of the paper that instead of standing as a facilitating factor to humanism among Africans,

the African religiosity rather has not only encouraged existential in-authenticity but also human and material exploitation and inhumanity.

Adopting an expository method to critically evaluate the African religiosity, the paper at the end shall not only add to the number of literature taking up the discourse of religiosity from an African perspective, but shall also expose what religion could really mean, what being religious could offer to humanity and equally how it could meet the demands of 'being moral' which is quite different from 'being religious'.

This paper is divided into sections: the abstract which is a condensed summary form of the entire work; the introduction that could be referred to as a more elaborated abstract; the section where the literary and ideal meanings and implications of religion are exposed. Following is the section presenting an African understanding of religion and how it bears on the African religiosity; after this comes the section where the fact of being religious is differentiated from being moral. The final section deals with evaluation and conclusion.

Religion as a Concept

The term 'religion' as a concept is conceived as a big shelter to divergent practices of various belief systems. Thus, the quality 'religiosity' is a universal one but under the influence of the creed that births the optimism referred to as religiosity. However, being religious is universal, but the point of concern is the driving force of one's religiosity. A conglomeration of this 'driving force' is what is referred to as 'fanaticism'

which has been misdirected to negative conception that has bred insecurity making it a point of attraction to humanity. Religion as a term etymologically implies ideas like ‘to bind’, ‘to unite, to link together’, ‘relationship’.¹ There are derivatives from these implications. The first which means ‘to bind’ implies that in religion, at least two entities are ‘bound’ together. This act of ‘bind’ stands for the covenant aspect of religion which must never be broken, but faithfully held high, and it equally foresees its sacredness, commitment and sincerity of both parties that are involved in the act of religion. The second which means ‘to unite, to link together’ implicates religion also as an activity where at least two different or unequal beings get themselves united or linked up as a group or even an entity of sort, as it were. This implies that the sense of seriousness, patriotism and duty-bound-nature are central in the acts of religion. No wonder a source reveals that in its Latin origin, the term ‘religion’ inheres that sense of ‘obligation, reverence’.² The third which means ‘relationship’ implies a sort of reiteration that as the involved parties are now conceived as being bounded, linked and united forming a sort of an entity, they are now in a relationship characterized by commitment, sincere-openness, sense of morality, reverence and most

importantly, ‘belief.’ Belief is the most essential phenomenon of religion. Put differently, without belief, religion has no essence, hence instead of reason or rationality as it is in philosophy, belief or faith is the fundamental tool and the end product of any activity of religion. Fundamentally, we can infer that religion is characteristically a relationship, link or bond that exists between at least two parties— man and the Divine.

There are several definitions of religion, however, following the fact of the involvement of the ‘invisible’ in religious affairs, definition according to creed and practices vary. On this view Metuh suspends his submission arguing that religious definitional variations follow from the fact that the object of religion is invisible and the spiritual beings who are not subject to observation are conceived in different peoples. Besides, the study of religion interests people with a widely differing interests as theologians, anthropologist, psychologists and sociologists, each of who see it from different perspectives³ Nonetheless, Omoregbe goes straight to argue that the term religion “has a specific meaning, and refers to a specific kind of activity which is in a category of its own. It refers specifically to that kind of activity which goes on between a man and a transcendent being (a deity) believed to exist.”⁴

¹ Bernhard Häring, *The Law of Christ*, Vol. III (New York: Newman Press, 1964), 111; Joseph I. Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion: Christianity and other World Religions in Dialogue* (Lagos: JOJA Educational Research and Publishers Limited, 2006), 3

² (*Oxford Dictionary of Current English*)

³ Ikenga E. Metuh, *Comparative Studies of African Traditional Religion* (Onitsha: Imico Publishers, 1987), 13

⁴ Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion*, 4

In other words, it is that “interpersonal relationship between a man and a transcendent personal being **believed** to exist.”⁵ On a similar scale, Cardinal Arinze has held subjective and objective views of religion hence he writes: “subjectively, religion is the very consciousness of dependence on a transcendent being and the very propensity or inclination to ... worship. Objectively, religion is a complex of truths, laws and rites by which man is subordinated to the transcendent being.”⁶ These subjective and objective perceptions of religion present religion as an affair that involves man and divinity through faith and as a whole exercise, guiding-norms and traditions concerned in it. At the extension of this definition, Idowu’s conception of religion comes very relevant. For him, religion entails the “belief in the existence of a supernatural ruling power, the creator and controller of the universe, who has given to man a spiritual nature which continues to exist after the death of the body.”⁷ Religion could also be seen as not only the relationship between man and divinity through faith, but also the relationship between man and sacred items of religion. Ugwu and Ugwueye hold that religion could also be defined as “the relationship

between man and what he regards as sacred. It is man’s recognition of a supersensible reality.”⁸ Of course the recognition of this supersensible reality goes with a lot of piety and commitment having acknowledged their supernatural influence on man. Nonetheless, the point remains that religion is an engagement, medium through which two parties— man and the Divine, respectively inferior and superior— relate and bond based on faith/belief, commitment and sincerity. This informs the definition of religion as “the belief in the existence of a god or gods, and the activities that are connected with the worship of them” or “one of the systems of faith that are based on the belief in the existence of a particular god or gods.”⁹

However, there are many scholarly definitions of religion based on the definer’s experience, background or profession. Some view it from psychological, sociological, theological backgrounds or even in accordance to the Marxist creed.¹⁰

Religion as must be acknowledged is essentially part of man’s nature, even on a daily basis. This is because man is naturally a moral being, and morality is a universal concept and transcends all religions and peoples. Suffice it to say that the

⁵ Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion*, 4

⁶ Francis A. Arinze, *Sacrifice in Igbo Religion* (Ibadan: Ibadan University Press, 1970), 8

⁷ Bolaji E. Idowu. *African Traditional Religion: A Definition* (London: SCM-Canterbury Press Ltd, 1973), 58

⁸ Christopher O. T. Ugwu and Luke E. Ugwueye, *African Traditional Religion: A*

Prolegomenon (Lagos: Merit International Publications, 2004), 3

⁹ *Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary* (8th edition)

¹⁰ Anayochukwu K. Ugwu, *A Philosophical Comparison between African Traditional Religion And Western Religions*, (Forthcoming)

sense of good and bad is innate in man; this innatism or moral consciousness arises from the voice of conscience in man which reacts to the attitudes of man. The self-consciousness of religious engagements therefore proceeds from the self-consciousness of morality which inheres in man. Religion can help man to find engagements that lead to moral consciousness, but it is neither the inventor of morality nor the initiator of its consciousness in man.

In concluding this section, it is pertinent to reinstate that religion as a concept is inherently good, however the creed inhered in its practice is a whole lot of concern. Supposedly, religion ought to play vital roles in reinstating humanism and ensuring human welfare. Giving his submission in view of this, Abbot has this to say: From the various religions, men accept answers to the secret enigmas of the human conditions which deeply-troubled the human heart yesterday as they do today. Man's nature, the meaning and end of our life, good and sin, the origin and aim of suffering, the way to reach true happiness, death, judgment and sanction after death, finally, the ultimate and ineffable mystery which envelops our existence where we came from and where we are going¹¹

Religion, as portrayed in the above citation, plays a vital role in providing solutions to human existential challenges. Put differently that central to religion is human welfare. It must not be forgotten that in religion, persuasion, psychological threats, or personal willingness

following self-conviction of the inferior being to encounter the superior being, play huge influences.

Significantly, it must be noted that religion is primarily all about man-divine relationship. The question of morality therefore comes secondary to this. While the primacy of activity of religion is relating between the inferior visible and the superior invisible, the question of morality is the focus on what is good and bad from a rational perspective. So, when the African is discussed with religiosity, he is only subconsciously carrying out the characteristic of religion which could generally be described as 'participation' in what is termed/described as 'religious'. But any religious engagement (religiosity) that entirely revolves around the religious meaning at its threshold (just relating, participating in the religious) is essentially empty; and that is the situation of the African in religion. Suffice it to posit then that religiosity negligence of morality from the perspective of rationality is substantially ill-religiosity. In other words, features of good religiosity fundamentally include: one, morality, and two, rationality. Rationality ought to discern on morality which will in turn discern on religiosity. And what are the central criteria of this moral discernment on religiosity? They include, one, the welfare of the community wherein both humans and non-humans exist and the whole expression of religiosity is carried out; and two, the upholding of humanism for the religious human, the

¹¹ Walter M. Abbot (ed.), *Documents of Vatican II*

(London: Godfrey Chapman, 1966)

African in this case must first exist and his/her welfare guaranteed/secured, before any expression of his/her possibilities like the concept of religiosity as contextually taken in this paper. Functionally, it is part of the contribution of religion to ensure this.

It has been pointed out above what, in reality, religion literarily means and implies. Religion depicts relationship between the visible and the invisible. But one point that inheres from this understanding is that, expectedly, the presence of the superior invisible being with which the inferior visible relates should stand as the bedrock of moral consciousness that inscribes in religion. That is to say that adding to the natural consciousness of what is good and bad in man, the central involvement of the divine in the whole act of religiosity should stand a place of reckon on religious affairs. This is because to relate is to be in ontological expectation of the outcome of the activities of the relationship. Put differently to mean that religion should be ontologically understood from the fact that there are forces in existence, and these forces proceed from a source, the supreme force. By these, the existing forces range in categories, and these forces respond to man in accordance with the level of morality inhered in each activity of relationship. In the religious relationship, these forces still exist and react to the activities which man engages in, in his religiosity. The presence of these forces is enough reason to stir up the consciousness of morality vis-à-vis religion. These forces are entirely represented in the divine being with which man religiously relates.

These forces (divine beings) with which man relates from a religious perspective, rewards man's activities shown in the activities of his religiosity. So, in religion or the religiosity of man, the consciousness of morality should be inhered following the presence of the divine who is ever ready to reward man. In other words, the divine being ontologically interacts with man in accordance with his moral consciousness. Any religion that should not intrinsically portray this is a religion void of the relationship with the invisible, and from such a stand point of view, should not qualify to be regarded as a religion for that is the etymological meaning and implication of religion as a term and concept. Such acclaimed religion or religious exercise should rather be best described as anything 'social'. This is the first point of the argument.

Again, the sense of humanism is a factor enough to the arousing of moral consciousness in man. The fact of core understanding of the sacredness of life, the sense that it is with fellow human being that one deals with in one's religiosity, the feeling of humanness of the fellow religious person is enough motivation towards being moral as a religious being. These are fundamental to the understanding of what religion really means and what religiosity implies.

Finally, the consciousness of what really exists is another factor. Man lives in a community, socio-ontologically communes with both fellow visible and invisible beings in the community, and so experiences both peace and war emanating as results from his living and his socio-ontological

affairs with other beings, all these in different communities still. The existence of man, the religious, the being whose religiosity is in consideration, is bound to the communities into which the world is divided. Thus, to visibly exist is to exist in communities of the world. Even to divinely exist is to exist in interrelationship with the visible beings and the world. Any being, whether visible or invisible that exists independent of the inter-communication between its world and the visible world and beings, is non-being, does not really exist. To exist therefore is to exist in a peculiar community and in interrelationship with the visible world and beings. The visible world and beings are the media, tools of manifestation of the reality of the existence of any being. Therefore, being implicates the idea of existence in a peculiar particular world, ontological communion with every other being which must get its manifestation not only in the invisible but also in the visible world, creation of effects from the ontological interrelationship with other beings, and finally, the feeling of the effects from the activities of the ontological interrelationship.¹² Put differently that essentially, *being* implicates *existence*, and existence in *worlds*, and beings in

the worlds essentially *intercommunicate*, and the world-intercommunications must create ontological *effects* which must be *felt* by beings.

African Understanding of Religion: the Implications of the African Religiosity

It is unfortunate that the African understanding of religion and the implication of religiosity take different and confusing perspectives. The African understanding of religion and his acclaimed religiosity are rather shallow; in that the fundamental knowledge is all about participation. The ontological aspect of being religious which should stand to bear on his religiosity is from his understanding of religion. The ontological understanding of the activities that make up 'religion' and the 'being' of religiosity is totally excluded from his real grasping of both religion and religiosity. Religion for the African is all about the relationship that characterizes the man-divine interaction described as religion. This relationship is mindless of whether it is entirely social, ontological or socio-ontological. And from this understanding breeds the version of religiosity that characterizes the African life. It is all about 'show yourself' and try to be seen 'participating'. Religion for the African becomes all about 'just

¹² Anayochukwu Kingsley Ugwu, *An Ontologico-Phenomenological Approach to the Meaning and Cultural Implications of Ala* (forthcoming); Cf. George Ohabuenyi Abah and Anayochukwu Kingsley Ugwu, "A Discourse on the Meaning and Cultural Implications of Ala to the Igbo," *International Journal of Integrative Humanism*, 13(1),

(2021), 205. <https://www.integhumanitatis.com/journals/integhum>; Cf. Anayochukwu Kingsley Ugwu and Gabriel Asuquo, "The Challenges of African Communitarianism in the 21st Century: An Igbo Perspective," *Nasara Journal of Philosophy*, 7(1), (2022), 83-6

identify as one and with the people’, ‘show yourself in a way that you are described as a member’. Attend the gathering, wear the uniform, say the prayer as stipulated, participate the number of times religiously obliged of you, pay the ‘religious’ bill or levy, do it that time you are religiously told/ordered to, do everything to demonstrate your participatory commitment and belongingness, no one sees the heart and so, no one can judge you. This is their sense of morality. When the Igbo African say *i bu ezigbo onye uka* (you are a good religious), it proceeds from his/her sense of judgment of your compliance with the ethics and doctrines of the church. The sense of morality which centres on the goodness and badness of an action or a phenomenon is for the Igbo African, the good or badness in complying with the religious ethics and doctrines. So when you do all these, you are then *ezigbo onye uka*, your *ezigbo-ness* (the sense of good and bad) lies in your compliance and this alone differentiates you from every other religious for whom the Igbo African would say, *onye obula bu onye uka* (every person is religious– hence everybody is consciously or sub-consciously guided by beliefs in something with metaphysical implication in his/her life with whom s/he relates). To acquire the *ezigbo-ness* of your *onye-uka-ness*, you must behave in rhythm with the religious ethics and doctrines. Upon this, your rightness and wrongness must be judged; that is obedience, that is humility, and without obeying and humbling yourself to those religious ethics, you are not *ezigbo onye uka* (a good religious). In the sense of complete and

genuinely participating in the ethics and doctrines of the church lies the African sense of morality. But they will never ask ‘who is the church’ who dish these ethics and doctrines, which I am obliged to obey so as to acquire my *ezigbo-ness* of my being religious. The church is not abstract. It is a conglomeration of authorities, powerful individuals who meet to decide for the church and its management. Among these authorities or body of authoritative people, is one human being at the global headquarters of each religious denomination. That of Catholic is in Rome, in the person of the Pope, and for Christendom, pilgrimage is made to Jerusalem where places are described as ‘holy’; that of Islam is in Saudi Arabia, though the headship divided between the Grand Imam for the Sunni Islam faithful, and the Grand Ayatollah for the Shia Islam faithful, and pilgrimage is made to Mecca where places are described as ‘holy’ also. This gives rise to religious synods. In this high fanatic consciousness, anything against these doctrines and stipulated ethics, even if it is similar, is not described as *ezigbo* (good/right) rather by the virtue of not being that, it is wrong. So, no matter the essentially similarity of the traditional African religion and the Western religions, especially Catholicism, it is *ife Arusi* (worshiping what could be described as ‘idolatry’), even when this religion is essentially same with the catholic creed and practices. So, they live in the Baconian idols where they refrain from castigating theirs just because it is ‘Western’ but castigate same

version elsewhere just because it is ‘African’ or ‘Asian’.

In the spirit of this fanaticism, Africans have turned into agents of disintegration and threats to the community. They have hidden under the umbrella of one religion or the other to bring chaos and disorganization, disobedience to social norms, cultural observances and traditions forgetting the ontological implications. In one community, a man in ‘deeper life’ with Christ refused to accord his parents their funeral cultural rites arguing that his deepened belief in Christ is against such. At death, he was beaten by the parent till he begins to confess, shouting and finally told the children that they shall never do anything about their burial and funeral ceremony without doing those of his parents’ which he has denied them. After this, he gave up the ghost. This is how Africans incur ontological negative reactions from the invisible on themselves who are still in the visible realm of existence.

In the spirit of the African religiosity, he commits suicide religiously, live in in-authenticity and commit murder. Is it not surprising how some Africans in “deeper life with Christ would reject blood transfusion even in a critical condition arguing that it is against their version of Christian creed. When people should be hustling, or resting in the night, Africans are busy religiously hustling in prayer grounds, shouting in praises and prayers and causing health crisis to themselves and being exploited by their lazy ‘religious heads’ who see them as commodities from which their livelihood comes. ‘Religious’

students embark on vigil even until the night preceding their exam dates, they turn classrooms worship arenas. In sickness, instead of embarking on medical care, the African religious rather embarks on prayer care and prescriptions. Africans turn every space, school, roadsides and streets, market squares, entertainment centres, uncompleted structures and even their own houses into religious grounds where praises and worships are religiously carried out. They have highest number of religious and religious centres yet the most corrupt and very inhuman that bloodshed is perpetuated under their religiosity and the most undeveloped as a result of physical and intellectual imprisonment. Where they are expressing their religiosity, they neither give priority to academics and believe in the intellectual productivity nor embark on hustling their way out through their inherent nature producing good things of life. An in-law would always complain of how his wife would, in the spirit of this religiosity, keep him hungry while in the farm, care less about their children’s welfare as she will proceed from school where she teaches to church programmes and then return home late at night. Children subsequently become wayward and highly vulnerable to accidents and some crimes like rape, secrete cultism and theft/robbery following the lack of parental care from the religious mother. They prophesy about good things but they do not do it; they like to enjoy good things that other people have built through their mental and physical struggle; they prefer to sleep day and night in the church or mosque soliciting for miracles. The

African religiosity is perpetuated by poverty of the mind and pocket, and that is why outside Africa, Africans face the reality and fall in the line with the mental and physical efforts of their host nations. Religiosity makes Africans consumers of good things proceeding from other people's physical and mental struggle. In the face of religion, the African is like a child, highly irrational. In this irrationalism, he brings out his colonial mentality, psychological enslavement where his only utterance is 'yes' without questioning. This breeds a sort of life characterized by in-authenticity expressed in fake, pretence and lies not just among pastors and their superiors but also the lay faithful provided the doctrinal status quo is maintained. Remarkably, this has facilitated neo-colonialism characterized by the master-servant relationship between the religious-superiors and the lower pastors and between the lower pastors and their parishioners/lay-faithful.

First, the fact that the domineering versions of religion and their practices which Africans practise today are not just foreign to their consciousness and culture, but also imposed on them, is worth considering. In Africa at large, there are sections of religions practised within either a huge or small number of adherents. However, few among them dominate others, and these, in addition to the African(Indigenous) Traditional Religion, include majorly Christianity and Islam and some fractions of other religions and their peculiar creeds. All these from their names are foreign to the traditional religion. Following this, they exist in

the sub-consciousness level of the people. So, the shallow understanding of these domineering, prevailing foreign religions could be traced to lack of understanding of the precepts by Africans. This fact is never hidden as there are not only versions of the scriptures and holy writings of these religions, but also different interpretations of the scriptures saying same thing but in different words. These fractions in the scriptural interpretation bear a lot as to its foreign and confusion to the African understanding of them.

The fact that they were subtly brought and imposed on Africans is another considerable factor. They were brought by foreigners to melt down, counter the aggression of African that could arise from the Western expression of inhumanity meted unto the African through the Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade, colonialism and neo-colonialism. They were impositions on Africans so as to instil the life of in-authenticity, incapacitation before the possibilities of their nature. The kind of peace preached and infused in the psyche of Africans is the one that will make them never to realize themselves till the generations after the people who experienced their inhumanity on Africans have all died. Going against this principle is violence and by this, the people involved are tagged heretic, disobedient to the 'mother' church and the cardinals of the religion involved. By this, a total dependent sort of life is inculcated in Africans. Everything from the west, the originators and always heads of their religions would equally be superior to anything Africans. The fruit, principle and self-

hate in implanted in Africans. He can never live well without consulting western proceeds.

It is from this angle that some see these domineering foreign religions as 'Dogmatic Doctrinal Configuration'. Put differently to mean a configured dogma which has indoctrinated to guide and imprison you to exist within the confines of those dogmatic principles. This exposes the intrigues of these religions as deception from the beginning till the end, and to cover this, they crown it 'Chi nwe ikpe' (God is the only (supposed) judge). So, from a fundamental critical cross-examination, religion for the African is socially conceived; it is to maintain a sort of socialization among a group, set of individuals tagged or described in a religious term. Morality attached to the African religiosity is a different case altogether. Thus, as Africans cry for politicking without morality in the continent which has bred a lot of human disaster and incurring of negative ontological reactions on Africans, so do they lament again for the African religiosity without morality which has bred another version of inauthenticity, existential non-fulfilment and inhumanity from both material and human resources. Many factors may be answerable to this reality.

No matter how religiously westernized the African is, his traditional religion exists within the core, or in the fullness, of his consciousness. He never forgot, and there lies his sincerity and sense of morality. This answers why no matter how foreign-religious he is described, his consciousness never left that of his traditional religion; he quickly and even unknowingly goes

back to it when he feels seriously challenged. Whenever the truth is highly needed from the African, he should be threatened with his traditional practices. He knows the reality and effectiveness of the rituals and activities there in. Persuading him or subtly drawing out the truth from him by reminding him that you as a victim would engage traditional means quickly rings seriously in his mind, and at this point, he would be compelled to say the truth and do the right thing. The African would consciously face the foreign religion and religious exercises to take an oath on falsehood, but would not find it easy doing same facing a traditional deity. A motorcycle was stolen on a Sunday morning following the carelessness of those early morning attendants who left the gate open when they left. As days passed by, the incident took the central discussion both in the yard and street which subsequently necessitated the starting of neighbourhood security days after. One day while discussing about the incident in the yard, a neighbour who never allowed other people in the yard to sleep well following her family's preparation for the early morning church service, a charismatic and Catholic communicant said, if it were (their) own motorcycle that was stolen, she would have gone traditional in the search and subsequently cast curse through a traditional deity. The belief is that justice is not just possible but also quicker in the traditional means than is in the foreign religions. The experience from countering the faith of this family is not limited to this family and from their own religious creed (Catholicism), such experience are numerous

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seen in other families and religious denominations. This is why Africans rush to traditional means in pursuit of resolving their existential challenges especially when they become harder, and many a times, they not only get it from there, but also the manifesting progress is clear. This experience is not limited to a set of individuals among the lay faithful, it is seen displayed by many church leaders under different capacities like Bishops, Cardinals, Deaconry, Catechism(Catechists), Father(Priest)hood, Brothers and Nuns, Papas and Mamas, Prophecy(Prophets and Prophetesses), Pastorals(Pastors), Seers and Visionists, Religious(Prayer) Warriors, etc. Most of the individuals under these capacities go traditional to augment their religious strength or even entirely depend on traditional methods for their religious progress. And they would crown it with 'give to Cesar what is Cesar's and to God what is God's' or 'you do not put all your eggs into one basket'. For them, just like the Elisha's fans would say, it is a mannerism towards 'double anointing portion'. Today most of these foreign religious ways of praying have taken the core form of all it is to be religiously traditional. All those practices initially described as fetish, diabolical, superstitious, idolatrous, and everything human hence it lacks any quality to be described divine or assume divine involvement are all the methods most of these foreign religions have adopted as ways to interact with the divine. Today sand particles, recognition and acts of reverence and respects for the departed living(dead founders of the family), pictures and

even cloths are requests and acceptable means (and sometimes in absentia) for praying for a person. All these were blackmailed just as items of cultural significance and ideologies for their practices were destroyed, all because they are originally African. But today, they have been westernized through foreign religions and brought back into the African religious system. What the African has rejected and consequently thrown through the door has been accepted even more dearly today and brought into the home through the window just because the name and descriptive quality 'African' has been erased from it and 'Western' has been inscribed on it.

Summarizing this section, it could be argued that factors behind such expression of religiosity which has turned the African as a bat that does neither a bird nor a rodent (flying nor ground animal) when it has to do with religion is in his/her self. On the one hand, the African is conscious of his/her Africanness and his peculiar and workable religious means of interacting with the divine. On the other hand, s/he is also conscious of his westernized African environment and which has been dominated by the foreign religion without which s/he would be blended diabolic, fetish and evil. At this point, he does neither know if to entirely follow the foreign religions which do not resolve all his peculiar existential challenges, nor to be entirely and proudly out to follow his traditional religious means through which means s/he is more comfortable addressing his/her existential challenges even if it would cost him/her to be blended fetish, diabolic, superstitious and evil.

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He becomes religiously a bat. This explains why they belong or socialize in the foreign religions but wholeheartedly practise the traditional religion. That is why they go traditional for protection and progress in life endeavours and even take the symbol or *Ogwu* (which has wrongly been interpreted as only charm and negatively) given to them even to the venue of the exercise of their faith in the foreign religions.¹³ Nonetheless, this is not to posit that African religious traditionalists have no way of displaying their own level of religiosity. Some fanatic traditionalists almost live and even turn to servers in the shrines just eating and drinking, tuning songs and shouting. Some of the African traditional religious priests and priestesses practically have no second address as all they would say about themselves is ‘I am a priest’. Inauthentically they would resort to lies and fake tales to clients and fellow fanatics who look for solutions to their existential challenges hence they seek for what they and their families would eat. By this, they desecrate the shrine, abuse and depower the efficacy of their working tools through which the invisible manifest. The invisible with which man religiously communicates detest dishonesty and inauthenticity which breeds exploitation through religious means.

Interrogating Religiosity with Morality

The question of value is essential in human existence, for it drives human actions to the self,

the other and the community at large. Primarily, the concept of morality is a focus on the goodness and badness of a thing/phenomenon. It raises questions as to what is good or bad, and how that which is bad or good is such. But the fundamental question regarding morality is: what is the standard at which judgment a thing/phenomenon could be described as bad or good? Put different: what qualifies a thing/phenomenon as moral or immoral? Who or what is the agent, the being behind the standard? Is morality a human product, culture rooted, an environmental factor, or a product of situation, or a judgment of motive or emotion, or a natural phenomenon? Is the morality-standard subjective or objective? These, among other questions, are fundamental issues of morality. This paper makes bold to posit that morality could be a product of some factors to include the following:

First, this paper maintains a rational position of morality. Rationality is the manifestation of human nature as a thinking being. It is a manifestation of the human being as a spirit, as it stands as a manifestation of the spiritual sphere of the human being. Rationality is very necessary in the discourse of morality for two reasons: one, to differentiate between ethics and norms and morality; and two, to address the why question for which an action/phenomenon is described moral. Majority of Africans, because of lack of knowledge, intellectual exposure and

¹³ Abah and Ugwu, “A Discourse,” 204; Cf. Ugwu, *An Ontologico-Phenomenological Approach*

(forthcoming)

idols from their cultural and religious backgrounds, cannot differentiate between morality and ethics. Their religious ethics is all there is to judge the goodness or badness of a thing/phenomenon. Once the religions into which they have been divided, tell them to do or say this or that, that becomes the right, and they would keenly wish or persuade others to go along with the directives stipulated by their religions ethics. This is one of the reasons behind their conceptualization of all there is to be religious, as participation. Because the ethics of the religion which have dominated them says you should go to Mass (religious service/gathering) every day, or that Mass is the highest prayer, or you must give offering or pay your tithe in the church or belong to religious pious groups in your church, reading the scriptures, saying prayers hundred times, carry out evangelization even at the road side, embark on 'dry' fasting every three to four days of the week, say the Rosary every day, go to corporeal work of mercy, receive the Holy Communion every day especially during Christmas, Easter, Annunciation and Assumption days, pray and attend Mass on the All Saints and All Soul's days, etc, doing all these is all there is to be moral, real child of God, and subsequently become a sure Heavenly candidate. In as much as they do and abide by the creeds, rituals and ethics of the religion in which they believe, then they are moral and must inherit Heaven. Their consciousness of morality is limited within the consciousness of participating in religious exercises, rituals and faith-professing. They will never ask why must they

pay tithe, and most necessarily to who? In a situation of sickness on a Sunday morning, the day they are religiously obliged to attend the Mass, why must they embark on fulfilling religious obligations and forfeit seeking for health attention? Is it the number of times they do religious rituals and prayers that matter or the heart with which they do even one? Why must their church/religion hold this or that culture or belief? By reasoning, what is the possibility of this or that religious belief being real? Could there be another way to re-conceive this or that religious belief? All these are important issues as they concern religion and morality.

Second, the paper takes on the discussion on how to ascertain, by rationality, why an action or a phenomenon is described as moral. The question of morality is the one of good and bad, and what are the bases for an action/phenomenon to be called good or bad? The knowledge of reality begins from this physical world to the world beyond. Morality as a reality does not start and end with being in good with the invisible. In fact morality should fundamentally be human oriented. It should start from ensuring good for fellow human beings and then transcend from humanity to divinity. To be moral is to be fundamentally moral unto humanity before divinity. To really maintain the consciousness of divinity starts from maintaining good with humanity. So, for an action or a phenomenon to be qualified or ascribed or described as moral, it must be favourable and recognize humanity as its primordial element. Any search for divinity that is void of humanity is really a flaw. Thus, the

recognition of fellow human being is the first step towards divinity-search or maintenance of moral quality.

The third branch is a discussion on the position that anything qualified to be ascribed morality must not stop from maintaining good for humanity, but also for community in which the human being lives. It can never be logically non-fallacious for an action to favour or maintain good for humanity while maintaining bad for the community. The well being of the community-residents portrays the healthiness of the community. A disaster to one of these is a disaster to both. The goodness of humanity implies the state of the community and when the community-state is bad, the goodness of humanity is fallacious and logically fallacious. In fact, the goodness of the community implies that of humanity occupying the community; and the badness of the community equally implies that of humanity occupying the community.

The fourth is the position that the sense of good for humanity and the community implies the good for every being in the community which co-exist both in the physical and non-physical realms of existence. When good is unto humanity, and proceeds unto the community, then it takes an ontological status to flow in that realm to include by affection, other realities existing with and among humanity in the community. By this, the good that will guarantee morality status of those actions, thoughts and speeches of every being becomes all-encompassing and holistic. Goodness or the moral-status of an action or a phenomenon flows

in no boundary, for goodness affects. In a state like this, every being in the community described as good shares and gets affected by the goodness of both humanity and the community where in humanity exists.

From this angle, it could be said that morality as a concept vital to human existence is more of objectivity than subjectivity. Man is never an inventor of morality. It only expresses in human actions, speeches and thought, and subsequently gets discovered by the human reasoning. It is after morality must have passed through these natural processes that it could be said to be inhered in certain existential facts like culture, norms, traditions, etc of the people.

Evaluation and Conclusion

This paper has been able to navigate through religion as a concept and religious engagement of humanity and divinity. It is an attempt to explore into religion as a concept and how it intrinsically implies an engagement, relationship between humanity seen as the inferior being; and divinity seen as the superior being. It has equally interrogated the African understanding of religion both as a concept and a practical way of life through which the invisible is approached. The paper maintains that the African understanding of religion is shallow though not without some factors responsible. This shallow understanding of religion stands as the basis for his religiosity which could essentially be described as all it could take to participate in religious exercises and gatherings. Finally, it has as well dialogued between what morality could mean and what religiosity could imply. It has as

well discussed what bases could an action or a phenomenon be described as moral. But on what bases are the enumerated religious exercises undertaken by Africans described as immoral then? Does it mean that religion as practised Africans is immoral? The problems with the African religiosity include:

The first one is the African sheepishness in adhering, following any foreign religion with which he is dominated. They follow religions that disorient them towards their own religion and when imbibed by their principle, behave in antithesis to the principles of their world-view and ontology. But from a critical cross-examination, these foreign religions are essentially with theirs, but they sheepishly follow. For instance, the African traditional religion makes use of the intermediaries (deities, martyrs, the dead (departed-living) (saints in the foreign religions), seasons and even symbols and imagery significantly expressing sacredness, and other religious implications). These foreign religions like Islam and Christianity especially the Catholic denomination make use of all these. Even when the Christian scriptures condemn such, Catholics among Africans would defend their own version of creed against both the adherents of other foreign religious faiths and the African traditionalists. Is it not confusing defending what is essentially same with yours just because it is ascribed 'foreign'? little wonder then it is said that religion is merely a cultural

understanding of the supernatural being(s), and that is why Arabs are majorly Muslims, Chinese are Buddhists, Indians are Hinduists, Europeans are Christians. Unfortunately only Africans keep searching for God or a god outside of their culture.¹⁴

The second is the African over-doing or carrying of these religions on their heads instead of their shoulder. By this, Africans claim holy art thou, more Christians and Judaists than the Israelis, more Muslims than the Saudi Arabians. Look at these instances. On one hand, the foreigners who brought foreign religions condemned the African way of life including religion and took away their deities and spiritual powerful religious elements and instituted forces, and explored (tapped) the inherent vital force in them progressively for their own betterment. On the other hand, the brainwashed and disoriented Africans grew up in the same faith, claim the ownership of the 'practicality' (but not the real 'originator' and 'ownership' of these religions) by becoming violent and destructive to the deities and instituted forces the African religious practices inhered, terming them yokes, diabolism and fetishes which deserve only destruction to their own loss in both exploring (tapping) the vital force for their own progress and also cultural and religious identities. Thus, which instance is preferable to the other?

The third is the level of inauthentic, irresponsible life Africans incurred on themselves through

¹⁴ A post made on a APPON (Association of Philosophy Professionals of Nigeria)

WhatsApp platform

their essentially morally empty religiosity. Morality is the bedrock of religiosity, and while this is lacking in religiosity, then the religious is only deceiving him/herself and risking unity with the divine in true sense of it. Religiosity without morality is likened to a house built on a castle, the religious lack solid foundation- the supposed divine support upon which the strength of his/her religiosity should stand. The reality, standardization and foundation of religion and the religiosity of the religious is morality without which the religious lives in emptiness and vulnerability to destruction and negative effectiveness of forces there are.

The fourth is the height of human and material exploitation that characterize their religiosity. The level of economic dialecticism as Karl Marx would maintain, under which religion is purported today among the religious is too amazing to the sense of religious morality and sane African. Generally, it could be said that the underlining reason behind their religiosity is materialistic, economy-driven, and for human satisfaction at the expense of the religiously brainwashed sheepish followers.

Finally, the fifth is their being less concern to the rightness or wrongness of their religious activities and how rationally justifying, could these activities affect humanism and the community not just of humanity but divinity in which beings exist. Majority of Africans are

highly religiously irrational that their sense of morality and rationality are incarcerated in the enthusiasm to do that which their religions order them to unquestionably do. That which their religion orders them to do is always morality and rationality in expression. This is one of the main roots of the terrorism religious engineered bedevilling not just Nigeria but also Africa at large. Even though some religions inherently in their scriptures encourage violence and inhumanity, but the poverty of the mind and pocket makes it more severe in Africa than any other continent of the world occupied by religious under different religions in the world.¹⁵

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